

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE AND SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOSOMATIC DISEASES

Narmetova Yulduz Karimovna

Associate Professor of Tashkent Medical Academy

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841748

Abstract. In this article, the manifestation of neurosis in patients with psychosomatic diseases, indicators of quality of life in patients, depression, the influence of somatic disease on the lifestyle of patients, as well as the dependence of alexithymia on the level of manifestation of neurosis are studied. Based on the results, practical recommendations were developed.

Key words: neurosis, depression, quality of life, lifestyle, alexithymia, psychosomatic diseases, pain intensity, vital activity, emotional activity.

In our study, we put forward a scientific hypothesis that the effect of any psychosomatic disease on the mental state of the patient varies in terms of the character of the disease, the characteristics of its clinical course, the prognosis of the disease, and its impact on the patient's socio-psychological adaptation to the condition of the disease, and the way of life.

Table 1 shows the results of studying the dependence of indicators of quality of life on the level of neurosis in patients.

Table 1

The results of the study of the dependence of indicators of quality of life in patients on the level of neurosis (Spearman's criterion, N=687)

Table with 2 columns: Scales, Neurosis. Rows include Physical activity, Role-playing activity, The intensity of the pain, General health, Life activity, and Social activity.

Emotional activity	-0,161**
Mental health	-0,086*
Physical component of health	-0,127**
The mental component of health	-0,179**
Life quality	-0,159**

Note: * - p<0.05; ** - p<0.01

According to the results of the study of the dependence of indicators of the quality of life on the level of neurosis in patients, no correlation was found in the intensity of pain and indicators of vital activity.

It was found that there is a negative correlation between the results of the physical activity scale of the quality of life questionnaire and the Heck and Hess method of determining the probability of neurosis (r=-0.096; p<0.05). In other words, the more a person's physical activity decreases, the more likely he is to fall into a state of neurosis.

It was found that there is a negative correlation between the results of the role activity scale of the quality of life questionnaire and the Heck and Hess method of determining the probability of neurosis (r=-0.165; p<0.01). Therefore, patients with reduced daily activities are more likely to fall into a state of neurosis.

A negative correlation between the general health indicator and the state of neurosis was found. It was found that neurosis increased as the patients' assessment of their current state of health and treatment prospects decreased.

Among the results of the study of the dependence of the social activity scale indicators of the quality of life in patients on the level of neurosis, it was found that there is a negative correlative relationship at the level of trust (r=-0.173; p<0.01). So, it was shown that the rate of neurosis increases as the social attitude of patients decreases.

When examining the relationship of the emotional activity indicator with the level of neurosis, a negative correlation was found (r=-0.161; p<0.01). The result shows that the long time spent by the patient in performing daily

activities leads to a decrease in the volume and quality of work, which leads to an increase in the state of neurosis.

The physical ($r=-0.127$; $p<0.01$), mental component ($r=-0.179$; $p<0.01$) and quality of life ($r=-0.159$; $p<0.01$) scales of the quality of life questionnaire Hek and it was found that there is a negative correlation between the results of Hess' method of determining the probability of neurosis. So, as the physical and mental health of patients decreases, neurosis increases.

Table 2 shows the results of the study of the dependence of depression in patients on the level of neurosis. In the table, it was found that there is a positive correlation between the results of the study of the dependence of depression on the level of neurosis in patients ($r=0.223$; $p<0.01$). An increase in the level of depression in patients with psychosomatic diseases causes an increase in the state of neurosis.

Table 1

Results of the study of the dependence of depression in patients on the degree of neurosis (Spearman criterion, N=687)

Note: * - $p<0,05$; ** - $p<0,01$

Scale	Neurosis
Depression level	0,223**

Table 3

Results of the study of the influence of somatic disease on the lifestyle of patients depending on the level of neurosis (Spearman's criterion, N=687)

Scale	Neurosis
The feeling of limited power and energy is	0,075
Deterioration of attitude to the patient in the family	0,112**
Limitation of Joy	0,182**
Deterioration of attitude to the patient at work	0,05
Limiting free time	0,121**
Career Limit	0,138**
Decreased physical attractiveness	0,054
Forming a sense of inferiority	0,07
Limitation of communication	0,033
Material damage	0,157**

Note: * - $p < 0,05$; ** - $p < 0,01$

Table 3 shows the results of the study of the influence of somatic disease on the lifestyle of patients depending on the level of neurosis. The influence of somatic disease on the lifestyle of patients was not determined depending on the level of neurosis in the indicators of limited strength and energy, deterioration of the patient's attitude at work, decrease in physical attractiveness, formation of a sense of inferiority and limitation of communication.

The effect of somatic disease on the lifestyle of patients depends on the level of neurosis on the joy restriction scale ($r=0.182$; $p < 0.01$). So, patients with low happiness have a high level of neurosis.

The influence of somatic disease on the lifestyle of patients depends on the level of neurosis, an indicator of deterioration of attitude towards the patient in the family ($r=0.112$; $p < 0.01$). A negative attitude towards the patient in the family leads to a state of neurosis.

The indicator of free time restriction is related to the degree of neurosis ($r=0.121$; $p < 0.01$). The lack of free time of the patient due to the disease leads to an increase in the state of neurosis.

Since the career restriction indicator depends on the degree of neurosis manifestation ($R=0.138$; $p < 0.01$). Our patients with psychosomatic disorders have a higher neurosis status as the career restriction increases due to their illness.

Since the material damage indicator depends on the degree of manifestation of neurosis ($R=0.157$; $p < 0.01$). In our patients with psychosomatic diseases, treatment due to their illness, an increase in the cost of medication is the cause of an increase in the state of neurosis in patients.

Table 4

Results of studies of the dependence of alexithymia in patients on the degree of manifestation of neurosis (Spearman criterion, N=687)

Scales	Neurosis
General level of alexithymia	0,157**
Difficulties in identifying emotions	0,154**
Difficulties in characterizing emotions	0,136**
Difficulties in external thinking	0,076*

Note: * - $p < 0,05$; ** - $p < 0,01$

The results of the study of the dependence of alexithymia in patients on the degree of manifestation of neurosis are presented in Table 4. It was found that at the general level of alexithymia ($R=0.157$; $p<0.01$), difficulties in detecting emotions ($R=0.154$; $p<0.01$), difficulties in characterizing emotions ($R=0.136$; $p<0.01$), their indications such as difficulties in external thinking ($R=0.076$; $p<0.01$) are dependent on levels of expression of neurosis. Increasing difficulty in describing how emotional-emotional states patients are experiencing causes the development of neurosis disorder. So the state of neurosis increases in our patient as our patients find it difficult to verbalize the negative states that are happening in him due to his illness to the doctor and loved ones

References:

1. Melibayeva, R. N., Narmetova, Y. K., Bekmirov, T. R., Bekmirov, T. R., & Abdumutalibova, M. M. (2023). Oilalarda Nevrotik Buzilishlar Sabablari Va Ularni Bartaraf Etish Usullari. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 695-699.
2. Karimovna, N. Y., Khasanboy, A., Iltifotkhon, A., Khabiba, N., & Adiba, M. (2023). Psychoemotional characteristics in psychosomatic diseases. The Scientific Temper, 14(04), 1444-1450.
3. Karimovna, N. Y. (2023). Psixosomatik kasalliklar bilan kasallangan bemorlar psixoemotsional sohasining jins xususiyatlari.
4. Narmetova, Y. (2023). FEATURES OF TURNING PAIN INTO A TRAGEDY IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHOSOMATIC DISEASES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(26), 42-44.

